

Focal ^{99m}Tc-MDP Uptake in Liver in Bone Scintigraphy in Patient with Hepatocellular Carcinoma: A Rare Case Report

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Abstract

Background: ^{99m}Tc-methylene diphosphonate (^{99m}Tc-MDP) bone scintigraphy is widely applied in the evaluation of both benign and malignant skeletal disorders. Nevertheless, extra-osseous accumulation of the radiotracer is an uncommon finding. Understanding the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms of such uptake is essential, as in certain contexts it may carry important diagnostic implications. In other cases, alterations in tracer biodistribution may have limited clinical relevance but can markedly compromise image interpretation. The purpose of this case report is to highlight these atypical patterns in order to minimize diagnostic errors and provide valuable clinical insights.

Case Presentation: A 45-year-old woman with a history of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), previously managed with multiple cycles of chemotherapy, presented with low back pain and paresthesia characterized by burning sensations in both lower limbs. A ^{99m}Tc-MDP bone scan was performed to exclude potential skeletal metastases. Unexpectedly, the scan demonstrated prominent radiotracer accumulation in segments V, VI, and VII of the right hepatic lobe.

Conclusion: This report discusses potential mechanisms contributing to such pronounced hepatic uptake. In this patient, the findings are most likely attributable to necrotic hepatic changes secondary to prior chemotherapy for HCC.

More Information

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Introduction

A clear understanding of the normal biodistribution of ^{99m}Tc-methylene diphosphonate (^{99m}Tc-MDP) is fundamental for the accurate interpretation of bone scintigraphy [7]. Under typical conditions, extra-skeletal activity is primarily observed in the kidneys and urinary bladder, reflecting renal clearance of the tracer. However, several reports have documented atypical non-osseous uptake, with proposed mechanisms including necrotic, hormonal, neoplastic, inflammatory, ischemic, traumatic, excretory, unbound radiotracer, and technical artifact-related factors [1]. Hepatic accumulation of ^{99m}Tc-MDP is uncommon and generally occurs in the context of radiopharmaceutical impurity, generator malfunction, or pathological processes. Such uptake has been associated with calcified areas within necrotic or proliferative fibrous tissue. In these circumstances, necrotic changes may promote passive deposition, hepatomegaly, tissue hypoxia, and accumulation of hemosiderin and calcium, all contributing to tracer retention. Additionally, ischemic injury disrupts cellular integrity, facilitating calcium precipitation within mitochondria and on denatured proteins [2].

Case Presentation

We present a case report of a 45-year-old woman diagnosed with hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) with lymph node metastasis. She was treated with complete six cycles of chemotherapy six months ago because the tumor was unresectable due to metastasis. Chemotherapy including Gemcitabine, Mannitol and Cisplatin (C1D1 of Gem-Cis chemotherapy) regimen was given to the patient in six fractions at 21-day intervals as a treatment. She tolerated chemotherapy well and was discharged with stable clinical and hemodynamic status. After six months of treatment, the patient complained of right-sided upper abdominal pain, low back pain (LBP) and a tingling burning sensation in both lower limbs. The patient had a history of hypothyroidism and was taking regular medication for that. To rule out the cause of pain, the patient was advised to have Contrast Enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT) chest abdomen with pelvis, Whole-body ^{99m}Tc-MDP skeletal scintigraphy and biochemical laboratory investigations. CECT revealed that there was hepatomegaly (~18cm) with normal attenuation and enhancement. Hepatic veins are normal. Intrahepatic biliary radicle (IHBR) was not dilated. Heterogeneously enhancing soft tissue density mass measuring 10.6 x 10.3 x 6.3 cm³ (CC x AP x TR) with non-enhancing areas within (likely necrotic) was seen involving IVb, V, VI and VII segments of right lobe with capsular retraction along segment V and VI; appearing to encase right hepatic artery & anterior branch of right portal vein and medially abutting left branch of main portal vein;

posteriorly abutting gall bladder with loss of interface with wall of gall bladder; inferior and medially abutting the antro-pyloric region with maintained fat plane. A few hyperdense lesions were noted within the mass area suggestive of D/D calcification (Figure 1).

Figure 1: CECT Axial Images Showing that there was Hepatomegaly with Heterogeneously Enhancing Soft Tissue Mass Measuring 10.6 x 10.3 x 6.3 cm³ (CC x AP x TR) with Non-Enhancing Areas within (likely necrotic) Involving IVb, V, VI and VII Segments of Right Hepatic Lobe

Whole-body ^{99m}Tc-MDP skeletal scintigraphy with SPECT/CT (Single Photon Emission Tomography/Computed Tomography) was performed following the intravenous administration of 20 mCi of ^{99m}Tc-MDP to visualize any bone abnormalities. The whole-body bone scintigraphy and SPECT/CT findings revealed that there was focal increased radiotracer uptake within the mass lesion in segments IVb and V, showing abnormally increased radio-tracer uptake in the liver, which is otherwise negative for any bone metastasis (Figure-2 and Figure-3).

Figure 2: The Whole-Body Bone Scintigraphy Revealed that there was Focal Increased Radiotracer Uptake in Liver Otherwise Negative for Any Bone Metastasis

Figure 3: SPECT/CT [A] Axial Image, [B] Coronal Image, [C] Sagittal Image, [D] Coronal SPECT Image Revealed that there was Focal Increased Radiotracer Uptake within the Mass Lesion in Segments IVb and V Shows Abnormally Increased Radio-Tracer Uptake in Liver.

Discussion

A thorough understanding of the physiological distribution of ^{99m}Tc -methylene diphosphonate (^{99m}Tc -MDP) is crucial for accurate interpretation of skeletal scintigraphy. In healthy individuals, tracer uptake is expected to be symmetric across the bony structures, while in children, additional prominent uptake is observed in the growth plates of long bones, reflecting normal skeletal development. Increased activity is also commonly noted in regions undergoing continuous remodeling, such as the acromioclavicular, sternoclavicular, sternomanubrial, sacroiliac, and pubic symphysis joints, as well as in weight-bearing articular surfaces of the shoulders, hips, knees, ankles, and feet, where degenerative changes are frequent. In adults, localized uptake is often identified in the maxillary and mandibular regions due to dental pathology, which stimulates reactive bone formation, and in the facial bones of patients with chronic sinus disease.

Physiological extraosseous distribution is typically confined to the kidneys and urinary bladder, owing to renal clearance of the tracer. Nonetheless, abnormal extraosseous activity may result from radiopharmaceutical preparation issues, biodistribution alterations, or uptake of unbound tracer in organs such as the thyroid, salivary glands, and gastrointestinal tract. Reports have described abnormal soft tissue accumulation of ^{99m}Tc -MDP in association with necrotic, neoplastic, hormonal, inflammatory, ischemic, traumatic, excretory, or artifactual processes [2]. On delayed imaging, unexpected uptake may also appear in the stomach, spleen, liver, muscles, or lungs. While the precise underlying pathology is not always identifiable, contributing mechanisms include normal anatomical variants, radiopharmaceutical preparation errors, drug

interference, extracellular fluid expansion, calcium metabolism abnormalities, tissue calcification, hyperemia, vascular permeability changes, iron deposition, ion exchange, binding to immature collagen, and attachment to denatured proteins or enzyme receptors [3].

Although focal hepatic lesions may occasionally be seen, diffuse hepatic accumulation of ^{99m}Tc -MDP is rare in nuclear medicine and remains an unusual diagnostic finding. There were a few cases reported as ^{99m}Tc -MDP uptake in the liver on whole body bone scintigraphy [4-5]. Nonetheless, all the cases reported with ^{99m}Tc -MDP hepatic uptake were not primary hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). Our case is unique and rare from all other cases reported previously because patients were diagnosed with primary hepatocellular carcinoma. Chemotherapy causes tissue necrosis in tumor cells and the patient has a history of chemotherapy taken. Literatures strongly concluded that non-osseous radiotracer uptake in the liver may be due to necrotic soft tissue [6]. In our case report, CECT findings revealed that there were non-enhancing areas within the mass (likely necrotic) seen involving IVb and V segments of right liver that may be the cause of focal increased ^{99m}Tc -MDP radiotracer uptake within the mass lesion in segments IVb and V in liver.

Conclusion

The detection of soft-tissue or extraosseous radiotracer accumulation on bone scintigraphy is considered atypical. While multiple factors may contribute to non-skeletal activity on ^{99m}Tc -MDP scans, the precise underlying pathology is not always identifiable. This report outlines several potential explanations for such findings; however, in the present case, the exact mechanism remains speculative.

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Declaration of Patient Consent

The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate patient consent forms. In the form, the patient has given her consent for her images and other clinical information to be reported in the journal. The patients understand that their names and initials will not be published, and due efforts will be made to conceal their identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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